

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF COMMERCIAL BANK LIQUIDITY MANAGEMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON THE ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18655537>

***Annotatsiya.** Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklari likvidligini ta'minlash bank tizimi barqarorligi va iqtisodiy rivojlanishning muhim omillaridan biri hisoblanadi. Raqamli texnologiyalarning bank faoliyatiga jadal joriy etilishi likvidlikni boshqarish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish, baholash va prognozlashda yangi metodologik yondashuvlarni talab etmoqda. Mazkur ishimizda tijorat banklari likvidligini ta'minlashning metodologik asoslari, jumladan, axborot texnologiyalari va zamonaviy boshqaruv usullarining roli tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, bank likvidligini samarali boshqarishning iqtisodiyotga ta'siri, moliyaviy barqarorlikni mustahkamlash, inflyatsion jarayonlarni nazorat qilish hamda iqtisodiy o'sishni rag'batlantirishdagi ahamiyati yoritib beriladi. O'zbekiston bank tizimi sharoitida raqamli iqtisodiyot talablariga mos metodologik yondashuvlarni qo'llash imkoniyatlari asoslab beriladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** raqamli iqtisodiyot, tijorat banklari, likvidlilik, foiz stavkalari, bank tizimi, valyuta kursi, liberallashtirish, chakana kreditlar, miqroqarz.*

***Abstract.** In the digital economy, **maintaining** the liquidity of commercial banks is an important factor for preserving the stability of the banking system and supporting economic development. The rapid introduction of digital technologies into banking activities requires the improvement of liquidity management mechanisms, as well as new methodological approaches to liquidity assessment and forecasting. This paper analyzes the methodological foundations of **commercial bank liquidity management**, with a particular focus on the role of information technologies and modern management methods. In addition, the study examines the impact of effective bank liquidity management on the economy, including its role in strengthening financial stability, controlling inflationary processes, and promoting economic growth. The paper also justifies the application of methodological approaches that meet the requirements of the digital economy in the context of Uzbekistan's banking system.*

***Keywords:** digital economy, commercial banks, liquidity, interest rates, banking system, exchange rate, liberalization, retail lending, microloans.*

Today, in the context of the digital economy, maintaining and managing the liquidity of commercial banks is one of the priority tasks for both the Central Bank and the banking system. The development of digital financial infrastructure requires the modernization of methodological approaches to bank liquidity regulation. According to international experience, central banks monitor commercial bank liquidity by conducting open market operations, managing reserve requirements, setting refinancing rates, and enhancing the efficiency of interbank markets through the use of digital platforms and modern information technologies.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been actively implementing measures aimed at modernizing the banking and financial system and ensuring financial stability. Based on

the Decree PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, “On the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022–2026,” the country has taken steps to ensure macroeconomic stability, strengthen the resilience of the banking system, and further liberalize monetary policy.

Furthermore, under the “Digital Uzbekistan–2030” strategy, approved by Decree PF-6079 on October 5, 2020, the digitalization of the banking system and the expansion of electronic financial services have been prioritized. This creates the need to introduce new technological tools that allow for real-time monitoring of commercial bank liquidity.

Economist V. Ivanov defines bank liquidity as “the ability of a bank to meet its obligations and clients’ credit demands on time and at minimal cost.” O. Zakharova describes bank liquidity as “the bank’s ability to fulfill its debt, financial, and off-balance sheet obligations.” According to the prominent economist J. Singh, liquidity is crucial for commercial banks to be prepared for deposit withdrawals and credit demand. At the same time, unexpected changes in cash flows pose a threat to bank liquidity.

S. P. Rouz provides a broader approach to the concept of bank liquidity, defining it as “the ability to obtain liquid assets at a favorable price, in the required amount, and at the necessary time.”

The various definitions of bank liquidity reflect the expanding scope of financial services provided by banks. In the context of the digital economy, bank liquidity manifests as the ability of a bank to mobilize sufficient liquid assets quickly when needed. This enables the bank not only to meet its current and future financial obligations on time but also to effectively satisfy the demand for digital financial services and consumer loans.

The growth in consumer loans extended to households is considered one of the inflationary factors supporting overall consumer demand. In the context of the digital economy, the observed stabilization trend in retail lending in 2024 is expected to continue in the coming years, allowing inflationary pressures to be mitigated through monetary channels. At the same time, in recent years, alongside the increase in loans to households, bank deposits have also experienced high growth rates. The ratio of deposits to loans in the household segment decreased from 62% in 2019 to 53% in 2023, while an increase in this indicator has been observed in the current year.

Figure 1. Ratio of Household Deposits to Household Loans, in Percent (%)¹

¹ Prepared by the author based on data from the official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.cbu.uz)

Due to the stabilization of retail lending and the high activity in savings, the ratio of deposits to loans through digital financial platforms is expected to reach 59% by the end of this year and 71% in the medium-term horizon (Figure 1). This process further emphasizes the need to apply digital methodological approaches in managing commercial bank liquidity.

This ratio is considered an alternative indicator of household debt burden, and its expected increase in the coming periods indicates a relative improvement in the financial condition of households and a certain reduction in debt burden. In the context of the digital economy, under conditions of declining inflation and a stable exchange rate, high real interest rates on deposits in the national currency serve as an important mechanism for attracting household savings in a stable manner. This, in turn, further emphasizes the need to improve methodological approaches in the process of maintaining and managing commercial bank liquidity.

**Table 1. Alignment between Commercial Banks’ Lending Levels and Liquidity Status
(Based on GDP Ratios), in Percent (%)²**

№	Type of Allocated Loans	2019- year	2020- year	2021- year	2022- year	2023- year	2024- year	2025- year *	2026- year *
1	Household Loans	7	8	8	10	12	13	13	13
2	Foreign Currency Loans	16	20	19	18	18	17	16	15
3	Corporate Loans	13	14	13	12	11	11	12	12
Total		35	42	40	40	42	41	40	40

*Note: * – Forecasted Values*

The share of household loans in total loans relative to GDP increased from 7% in 2019 to 13% in 2024. As retail lending stabilizes, this indicator is expected to remain largely unchanged in the coming years. At the same time, the increased activity of domestic savings is expected to maintain a declining trend in the dollarization of loan portfolios. Specifically, the share of foreign currency loans in GDP is projected to decrease from 20% in 2020 to 15% in 2026 (Table 2). This process further emphasizes the need for methodological management of commercial bank liquidity and the effective use of digital financial instruments.

² Prepared by the author

Figure 2. Dynamics of Bank Loan Interest Rates³

At the same time, due to the low alignment between the Central Bank’s key rate and commercial banks’ loan rates, the Central Bank introduced alternative prudential measures. In particular, the “Regulation on the Adequacy of Commercial Bank Capital,” adopted on June 13, 2015, and registered with the Ministry of Justice on July 6, 2015, under No. 2693, was updated starting in 2020.

According to the new regulation, differential risk weights were introduced for loans granted to legal entities and individual entrepreneurs. This measure is aimed at discouraging excessive and unjustified lending while promoting sound lending practices. The new framework establishes the following norms:

- If the loan rate does not exceed the Central Bank’s key rate +6%, the risk weight is set at 100%;
- If the loan rate is between +6% and +9% above the key rate, the risk weight is set at 150%;
- If the loan rate exceeds the key rate by more than +9%, the risk weight is set at 200%.

This regulation incentivizes banks to lower their loan rates, as higher risk weights reduce the capital adequacy ratio. As a result, risks that could negatively affect a bank’s financial stability and liquidity are mitigated, thereby enhancing the ability to manage commercial bank liquidity effectively from a methodological perspective.

These changes can be observed from the data. Specifically, starting from 2020, the amendments introduced in the above-mentioned regulatory document had a significant impact on the interest rates of loans granted by banks. At the same time, a key challenge that limits the influence of the Central Bank’s monetary policy instruments on market interest rates is the high share of state ownership in the banking system.

In conclusion, this regulation helps to establish a stable financial base in the national currency (som) within the banking system, thereby increasing the capacity of commercial banks to finance the economy in the local currency. In this process, the use of domestic savings as a primary resource expands, enabling commercial banks to manage liquidity effectively from a methodological perspective and ensuring financial stability in the context of the digital economy.

³ Prepared by the author based on data from the official website of the CBU Central Bank

Figure 3. Ratio of Allocated Loans to GDP, in Percent (%)⁴

The share of household loans in GDP is expected to increase from 7% in 2019 to 13% in 2024. As retail lending maintains its stabilization trend, this indicator is projected to remain largely unchanged in the coming years. At the same time, increased domestic savings and a continued decline in the degree of loan dollarization are anticipated. As a result, the share of foreign currency loans in GDP is expected to decrease from 20% in 2020 to 15% in 2026 (Figure 3).

In the context of the digital economy, the regulation of commercial bank liquidity through monetary policy instruments has a significant impact on the economy. It is crucial for banks to meet the real demand of households quickly and efficiently when managing their liquidity, as the faster customer demands are fulfilled, the more stable bank liquidity remains. At the same time, bank liquidity cannot always be maintained at a maximum level; keeping it at a stable level helps balance the capitalization of bank products and supports economic growth. Consequently, the methodological monitoring and management of liquidity in commercial banks becomes a key factor for economic stability and development in the digital economy.

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